

Roadmap Engagement Approach

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Efforts to understand current practices, limitations, and the vision for intelligent watersheds (IWs) were organized around a particular use case: intelligence supporting hydropower-related decisions. This includes decisions made by owners/operators as well as those with objectives that intersect with hydropower operations. Integral to the project philosophy was deliberate engagement with diverse stakeholder groups who are broadly interested in hydropower and other water management decisions. Expertise was gathered from researchers (academia, National Laboratories, and industry), tribal resource managers, state and federal resource managers, environmental advocates, hydropower operators, and technology developers. These stakeholders covered a variety of unique perspectives reflecting differences in interests, geographic jurisdiction, and scientific sectors.

Stakeholder engagement followed a phased approach. The *first phase* of consultation focused on defining gaps and opportunities relative to the technologies that support IWs. A virtual engagement process was adopted involving interviews with individual subject matter experts. Our engagements followed a semi-structured interview approach. Specifically, interview discussions were guided according to the following broad questions, specific to their organization’s objectives:

What is the current state-of-the-art for creating, managing, or using data?

What is a realistic vision for more intelligent watershed systems in the future?

What are the impediments and/or gaps to achieving this vision?

What are potential solutions, including emerging techniques?

Key to success was finding the right experts to interview. The interview selection process required full consideration of the data-to-decision spectrum including data creation, management, and analytics/use, which spans multiple sectors including climate, water, environment, energy, and society. This creates a functional matrix (Table 1) in which the component elements contain both distinguishing (e.g., unique data types) and unifying (e.g., similar data access challenges) features.

Table 1. Project efforts were organized by sectors (rows) and data-to-decision spectrum (columns). Examples of components are provided, but are not exhaustive.

	Data creation (monitoring, in situ/remote sensing)	Data management and informatics (quality assurance, visualization, etc.)	Data analytics and use (process-based or machine learning modeling, forecasting, simulation, etc.)
Climate: Precipitation, temperature, evaporation, climate change	Rain gauges, weather radar, satellites, flux towers	Effective management and knowledge discovery of large datasets	Near-term forecasts, long-term projections

Water: Surface, snow, and groundwater hydrology, rural and urban water systems	Streamflow gauges, well monitoring, water use surveys	Standards for hydrographic linkages/river network representation	Rainfall-runoff, routing, water management, hydrodynamic models
Environment: River/lake/reservoir ecosystems and quality	Water quality sampling, habitat surveys	Data portals for multi-year environmental surveys	Water quality, physicochemical, biodiversity models
Energy: Power plants, transmission, other energy supplies	Utility monitoring, consumer meters	Secured data sharing mechanism for sensitive and proprietary data	Cost of production, scheduling, long-term resource planning models
Society: Populations, policy, demands	Census, economic survey, land use	Flexible data management system for diverse types of social-economic data	ML/AI behavioral models, agent-based models

Guiding the **second phase** of stakeholder engagement was the recognition that important linkages, synergies, and overlaps exist across the singular perspectives of the individual experts interviewed. Toward this end, two virtual meetings were held to synthesize the Phase 1 results in a group setting. Again, meetings used a virtual format, but this time as a series of group meetings involving two, two-hour sessions. Participants included several who were interviewed in Phase 1 plus additional contacts identified during Phase 1 discussions. During the meetings, participants divided (self-selected) into groups organized around key IW use-cases: water resource management and planning, water and climate, environmental challenges, water and energy governance/policy, and community intersections with energy use and environmental or natural resource management. Interactive whiteboards were pre-populated with results from Phase 1, allowing Phase 2 participants to comment on and build on the previous work.

A **third phase** of stakeholder engagement explored issues related to the sharing and communicating of information within a watershed selected for a case study. Here, an individual basin perspective was taken where local stakeholder experience was the focus (e.g., hydropower owner/operators, river managers, electric utility operators, farmers, city managers, and federal/state/local agencies responsible for data collection and resource management). While we recognize that social, institutional, and practical barriers vary widely among different basins, this engagement enabled a first-of-its-kind assessment of non-technical aspects of IWs that can be carried forward in the subsequent development of IW initiatives.

The Upper Colorado River Basin was selected for the case study, in part due to the hydrologic, energy system and challenges related to governing the operations of this watershed with a variety of stakeholders at the federal and regional scales. Here, interviews were carried out in a virtual, small-group setting. Focus groups were organized around particular issues, (e.g., river operations, hydropower, environmental management) and scopes (e.g., whole basin or regional, community, or local perspectives). The virtual whiteboard approach was again used following a defined set of questions. Generally, the questions were aimed at understanding their decisional authority; the information and tools that they rely on to make their decision; the manner in which they access the information and tools; how they communicate their decisions; and the roles that members of the public and those outside of direct decision-making play in their operating and management decisions.

During the three phases of stakeholder engagement, we **identified gaps** in the current flow of information from data-to-decision and identified interdependencies between systems and processes. We documented what decisions are made and where risks, vulnerabilities, or failures exist because of disruptions in the flow of information or disconnects between processes or systems and data consumers/decision makers. The goal was to describe the range of gaps observed and highlight those that are shared among different stakeholders and regions/basins.

PHASE 1 CODING

Interview notes were combined into a joint database. Each respondent's notes were distilled into comments distinguished according to a specific thought or concept. A total 454 unique comments were extracted from the notes. Inductive coding was used to identify common themes across the different respondents. Inductive coding is an approach to data analysis that involves reading and interpreting raw contextual data to develop themes, concepts, or a process model. This is accomplished by assigning a digital code to each comment to facilitate grouping of related ideas.

A five-digit code was utilized to analyze the database of comments. The first digit codified the system that was referenced in the comment (data creation, data management, data use). The second digit related to the referenced sector (climate, water environment, energy, society, and social systems). The third digit was used to designate the state of technology readiness (state-of-the-art, emerging solution, gap, impediment). The fourth digit codified the specific technology referenced, while the fifth digit was reserved as a descriptor of the technology (e.g., remote sensing describes a particular type of snowpack monitoring).

Results indicated that responses were relatively balanced across the "intelligence" spectrum. The second digit provided similar insight into the breadth of sectoral coverage of the codified comments. Here, almost half of the comments were general in nature (not specific to a particular sector). Otherwise, there was a strong skew toward the water sector which makes sense given that water touches all the other sectors in this watershed context. Comments for all other sectors are relatively balanced. The third digit addresses technology readiness. While coding this particular digit it became very clear that the lines between State-of-the-Art and Emerging Solution were impossible to uniquely distinguish. Distinguishing between Gap versus Impediment was similarly difficult. As such, results should be interpreted on the basis of Solutions (State-of-the-Art and Emerging Solution combined) and Gaps (Gaps and Impediments combined). The result is roughly twice as many Gaps as Solutions were given.

The fourth digit codified the technology referenced by a particular comment. Results indicate that numerous technologies were referenced, distributed across data creation, management, and use. Specifically, 46 unique technologies were identified. Twenty-nine referenced data creation technologies (156 instances); four IT technologies (97 instances); and thirteen different data-use technologies (169 instances). The most commonly referenced technologies included shared databases (87), decision making (45), water management modeling (37), forecasting (20), intelligent systems (20), snow monitoring (14). Specific technologies referenced and their counts are provided in Table 1.

The fifth digit served as a descriptor of the technology. These descriptors provided additional insight into the application of referenced technologies. Forty-three unique descriptors were identified. The most commonly referenced include collaboration (36), controls and standards (36), ground measurement (36), AI/ML (23), funding/incentives (24), and remote sensing (26). Specific descriptors referenced and their counts are provided in Table 2.

When considered as a whole, a few general insights emerge. In almost every case, a given "technology" was referenced as both a gap and a solution. The two most common themes repeated by roughly half of respondents were: accessible databases utilizing a set of common data standards; and tools to support decision making in an environment of collaboration, engagement, and clear articulation of the science. The challenge for IWs is as much about implementation/execution as the lack of technology.

Table 1. Comment counts related to the technology referenced (fourth digit).

Technology	Count
Technology not Mentioned	8

General	58
<u>Data Creation</u>	
Streamflow	19
Snow	14
Water Rights	11
Water Quality	11
Utility Data	7
Irrigation	6
Reservoir Data	6
Geospatial Data	5
Env. Health Data	4
Groundwater	4
Water Use	4
Hydropower Gen.	3
Evapotranspiration	3
Disturbance	3
Agriculture	2
Cultural Data	2
Land Cover	2
Topography	2
Soil Moisture	2
Precipitation	2
Aquatic Species	2
Weather Data	1
Weather Modification	1
Water Vapor	1
Supply Chains	1
Flood Data	1
Ice	1
Infrastructure Maintenance	1
Algae	1
<u>Data Management</u>	
Shared Databases	87
Telemetry	4
Cloud Computing	2
Computing Resources	2
<u>Data Use</u>	
Decision Making	45
Water Management	37
Forecasting	20
Intelligent Systems	20
Environmental Management	15

Social dynamics	12
Coupled Water Energy Modeling	8
Automation	5
Precipitation/Runoff Modeling	3
Biogeochemistry	2
Development	2
Carbon Budget	1
Water Quality	1

Table 2. Comment counts related to the technology descriptor referenced (fifth digit).

Descriptor	Count
No Descriptor	15
General	45
Ground Measurement	36
Collaboration	36
Data Controls and Standardization	36
Remote Sensing	26
Better Funding/Incentives	24
AI/ML	23
Information Integration	22
Engagement	21
Multi-modal	20
Communication	14
Multi-Scale Issues	13
Extreme Event	13
Testbed	11
Proprietary	9
Climate Change	9
Access	8
Awareness	7
Lack Expertise/Capacity Building	7
Policy	6
Lack of Confidence	6
Visualization	5
Lack Knowledge of Data Limitations	5
Long-term Maintenance	5
Conflict	4
Uncertainty	3
Ariel Drones	2
Sampling Strategy	2
Workforce Development	2

Cameras	2
Training	2
Valuation	2
Research-to-Operations-to-Research (R2O2R)	2
Seasonal	1
Daily	1
Outside the box thinking	1
Metrics	1
Wildfire	1
Security	1
Smart Meters	1
Edge Computing	1
Version Control	1
Computational Power	1
Model Simplification	1